

MEASURING THE RIPPLE EFFECT OF POOR SLEEP HABITS ON STUDENT'S STRESS LEVEL

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ABSTRACT

Sleep holds immense significance in our lives, intertwining with both our physical and mental health. Presently, the pursuit of academic excellence and the surge in digital advancements have notably influenced students' lives, notably affecting their sleep routines and general welfare. The repercussions of inadequate sleep among students extend far beyond mere tiredness; it creates a domino effect that markedly heightens their stress levels, subsequently affecting their academic performance and overall quality of life. This study examined the sleep behaviors of Grade 11 and 12 students enrolled in the Humanities and Social Sciences Strand, involving 75 participants who completed a comprehensive survey questionnaire. The survey outcomes shed light on their demographic profiles, sleep patterns, the impact of insufficient sleep, and the strategies employed by students to counter its effects. Through meticulous analysis employing descriptive statistical methods, the study revealed diverse sleep patterns among Humanities and Social Sciences students, with a majority experiencing poor sleep quality. Moreover, it uncovered various coping mechanisms employed by these students to mitigate the adverse effects of inadequate sleep. Ultimately, the study underscores the profound impact of poor sleep habits on the overall well-being of students in this academic domain. The findings of the research highlight the necessity of focused interventions and support networks inside educational institutions to raise students' performance in school and overall quality of life. The findings may help educators, parents, and policymakers put strategies into place that will help students with sleep-related problems and improve their health and academic performance.

Keywords: *sleep habits, coping techniques, students, academic performance, sleep quality*

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the pursuit of academic excellence and the rise of digital innovations has influenced the lives of the students, particularly their sleep patterns and overall well-being. Late- night study sessions, paper works, meetings, and school related activities are the main priorities of students rather than the advised seven to nine hours of sleep. Indeed, sleep plays a pivotal role in our lives, as it relates to both our physical and mental health. Among the various demographic groups, students, specifically those in senior high school and college, often face challenges in maintaining healthy sleep habits. This has led to the continuous and growing issue of erratic sleep schedules and poor sleeping habits. The effects of poor sleep among students go beyond simple exhaustion; it includes a ripple effect that significantly impacts students' stress levels and, consequently, their academic performance and overall quality of life.

In the study conducted by Hirshkowitz et al. (2015), they have mentioned that every individual must have seven to ten hours of sleep to gain energy and be able to function properly. Although this data is not standardized and there are handful studies which state the effectivity of it. Additional studies can be conferred to further expand the number of sleeps. Depending on different factors that can be considered towards it like the age, sex, lifestyle and the like. However, most students are not getting the right amount of sleep they need. This can be seen by the fact that students do a lot of schoolwork and activities which can be a factor in the decline of their sleep time.

Recent statistics show that 97% of teenagers do not achieve the recommended amount of sleep (Statista Research Department, 2018). Accordingly, a medical news report from the US even stated that this growing concern on lack of sleep is largely due to stress, with 68% of students staying awake due to school-related activities Kim et al. (2018). Only 30% of students manage to get eight hours of sleep a night, which is the recommended amount of sleep. Lastly, about 20% of students pull all-nighters at least once a month. In the Philippines, sleep deprivation is one of the major growing concerns. As per the Healthy Living Index Survey (2016), the Philippines has one of the highest rates of sleep deprivation in Asia, with 46% of Filipinos not getting proper sleep and 32 % sleeping for less than six hours. This can hinder the daily performance of a person since sleep is vital towards the proper functioning of one's body.

This chronic lack of sleep has a detrimental impact on productivity among Filipinos, as noted in the study of Sygaco (2020). The lack of sleep has huge negative impacts on day-to-day activities, particularly academic performance. Considering the above-mentioned data, lack of sleep can risk health and the academic performance of the students. Students can perform low during their classes if they don't have the necessary amount of sleep. While chronic diseases can emerge if the student doesn't have the latter. Stress levels and different psychological problems can emerge due to sleep deprivation.

Hence, the major aim of this study is to investigate the ripple effect of sleep deprivation on one's stress level.

To this day, there is a scarcity of literature and research in the Philippines that delves into the consequences of poor sleep habits, particularly regarding students' stress levels. There is only a limited number of literatures that explores this topic and the global studies available are also outdated. The existing research on the ripple impact of inadequate sleep has prompted the researchers to pursue a comprehensive study to thoroughly evaluate the ripple effects of poor sleep habits on the stress levels of students. This study primarily aims to shed enlightenment on the intricate relationship between students' sleep habits and their experience of stress. By systematically understanding the associations and interconnections between sleep patterns, sleep habits, and stress, this study aspires to provide valuable insights into how these factors affect various aspects of students' lives and particularly contribute to their overall quality of life.

Unveiling the factors that constitute a student's stress level.

In the study conducted by Kosheleva et al., (2015), results showed heavy workload, lack of sleep, and deadline pressure as common factors of stress in their studying. The study found several stressors that had a huge impact on how well students performed in school. The numerous and continuous tasks that were frequently too much for students to handle were one of the stressors mentioned. This can be seen as a hindrance towards the learning development of the students given the fact that students who don't have the appropriate amount of sleep find it difficult to comprehend the lessons shared with them. Subsequently, in the study of Nollet et al. (2020), they found out that sleep deprivation and stress reciprocate with each other. Since if a person doesn't have an ample amount of sleep it can result in stress since our body's mechanism to adapt with the problem inside our body. In addition, if a person encountered stress it can result in poor performance specially on students who are sleep deprived.

Lack of adequate sleep made maintaining a challenging academic curriculum much more difficult. Students also struggled with the pressure brought on by approaching deadlines, which added to their general state of academic pressure, anxiety, and stress. These stressors can cause a person to have anxiety plus the factor that students don't have the appropriate amount of sleep just to do their different schoolwork. Social aspects also affect students' stress levels which include bullying and peer pressure. Alotaibi et al. (2020) have indicated that there is a correlation between elevated stress levels and reduced academic achievement. Nevertheless, suitable coping mechanisms have been demonstrated to assist learners in managing the adverse effects of psychological distress. This means that there is a reciprocation between the stress level and academic performance due to lack of sleep among the students. The aftermaths of this one can be detrimental to the student's mental health and their academic performance.

Poor Driven Academic Achievements Caused by Stress

Stress caused by sleep deprivation can produce numerous impacts on a person. Specifically, students since stress can deescalate the level of academic engagement and achievement of the latter. According to Pascoe et al., (2020), academic stress influences secondary and tertiary students' mental and physical health and leads to a variety of academic concerns. This claim is alarming since the students aim is to attain good grades, but the aftermath is their health being at risk due to various factors. Increased levels of academic stress generally result in poor academic performance. Students who experience high levels of academic stress find it difficult and challenging to perform at their best in class. Stress produces a variety of issues, including trouble paying attention and low motivation, all of which interfere with learning and academic progress. Those effects can severely hinder knowledge acquisition and even dismantle the learning outcomes of the students.

As per the result in the study conducted by Faizi et al. (2015), in India students, respectively, experienced high or extremely high levels of exam anxiety and academic stress. Due to their midnight reviewing and high expectations from their environment. Though all students expressed high levels of academic stress, the stress levels of those with lower grades were higher than those with higher marks. Azad et al. (2015) indicated in their study the significance for educational institutions to address stress as it hinders students' ability toward their educational objectives. Apart from prioritizing overall learning outcomes, it is equally crucial to consider the welfare of every single student. Additionally, educational institutions can also consider a variety of factors why students experienced academic stress that can result in poor academic performance.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the ripple effect of poor sleep habits on students' stress levels. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. How may the demographic profile of the senior high school student respondents be described in terms of:
 - 1.1. sex.
 - 1.2. age.
 - 1.3 Grade/Year Level
2. How does the respondent's demographic profile, such as sex, gender, strand, and grade level, influence their sleep habits and stress levels?
3. What are the students' sleep patterns, including the average bedtime, sleep duration, and common sleep habits on both weekdays and weekends?
4. How does the relationship between students' sleep habits and stress levels impact various areas of their lives, including academic performance, mental health, and their general state of well-being?
5. What coping techniques do students use to lessen the adverse effects of poor sleep habits on their stress levels?

METHODOLOGY

This study was carried out using a descriptive-quantitative approach. According to Apuke (2017), quantitative research is an organized approach to gathering and interpreting data from various sources. In response to this, Watson (2015) stated that to generate results, quantitative research employs mathematical, statistical, and computational. Meanwhile, in the lens of Siedlecki (2021), a descriptive research approach is used to gather information from a group of respondents. It has many advantages and benefits for data collection and analysis. This design will be employed by the researchers since the main purpose of this study is to measure the ripple effect of poor sleep habits on students' stress. In terms of the study's participants, the senior high school students of Humanities and Social Sciences Strand (HUMSS) at a higher educational institution situated in Pampanga, Philippines were recognized as the respondents to the study.

There were 75 identified respondents in the quantitative phase of the study. The said number of respondents answered the survey questionnaire. Subsequently, this study employed a survey questionnaire as the main data-gathering instrument. The questionnaire contains twenty-one (21) questions. The questionnaires are distributed to the respondents. In gathering the data coming from the respondents, the researchers carefully considered the research ethics as well as the proper data gathering procedure ensuring that all the data garnered will be used solely for academic purposes only. Meanwhile, the responses gathered from the survey questionnaires of senior high school students underwent statistical analysis, aligning with the study's data requirements. Descriptive Statistics is used to summarize data in an appropriate and relevant way by summarizing the primary details, according to Mishra et al. (2019). Descriptive Statistical Analysis was chosen by the researchers to assess the impact of inadequate sleep habits on Grade 11 and 12 students' academic performance, physical and mental health, and overall well-being. This method simplifies the gathered data using charts, graphs, and tables, effectively aiding in the comprehension of information from the respondents.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Sex

Table 1 indicates the respondent's demographic profile. 30 of them are male and 45 of them are female. Most of the respondents are female, with 60 percent over the whole percentage, while the male respondents are 40 percent over 100 percent. 60 percent females and 40 percent male.

Age

Table 1 presents the demographic profile distribution of the respondents in the study, encompassing individuals within the age range of 16 to 19. 28 percent of the whole population is under 16 years old, which consists of 21 respondents, while 49.33 percent of 100 are under 17 years old, which consists of 37 respondents. 20 percent of the population is 18 years old, which consists of 15 respondents, and the remaining 2.67 percent are 19 years old, which consists of 2 respondents. Most of our respondents are 17 years old, the sum of all the percentages is equal to 100 percent.

Grade/Year Level

Table 1 shows the frequency distribution and the percentage of the grade or year level of the respondents involved in this study. These are the senior high school grade 11 and grade 12 students under Humanities and Social Sciences Strand. The 31 respondents are grade 11 students, which is equivalent to 41.33 percent of the population, while there are 44 respondents who are grade 12 students, that is equivalent to 58.67 percent.

Table 1. *Frequency Distribution and Percentage of the Respondents demographic profile*

<i>Demographic profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>%</i>
Sex		
Male	30	40%
Female	45	60%
Age		
16 y/o	21	28%
17 y/o	37	49.33%
18 y/o	15	20%
19 y/o	2	2.67%
Grade/ Year Level		
Grade 11	31	41.33%
Grade 12	44	58.67%

Demographic Profile's Influences on Students Stress Level

According to the gathered data from the researchers, a mean of 3.08 and a standard deviation of 0.77 (agreed) that the academic strand that the respondents are enrolled in affects their sleep patterns and overall stress. According to Bianzon et al. (2024), the Humanities and Social Sciences Strand is for learners who aim to take up journalism, communication arts, liberal arts, education, and other social science-related courses in college. With this, HUMSS students often face much schoolwork including written work, reporting, and performance tasks. Table 2 also shows a mean of 2.67 and a standard deviation of 0.87 (agreed) that their grade level has a significant impact on their sleep quality. Furthermore, a mean of 3.13 and a standard deviation of 0.71 (agreed) that their stress level is highly influenced by academic requirements. In the study conducted by Bergin & Pakenham (2016) it was found that academic commitments, such as an abundance of homework, strict deadlines, and high-performance expectations, significantly raise stress levels. While, in the question "Does your gender play a role in how stressed you are as a student?" There is a mean of 2.41 and a standard deviation of 0.86, indicating a disagreement. Overall, the combined results show that demographic profile has an impact on the stress level of the students with a weighted mean of 2.84 indicating agreement.

Effect of poor sleep habits on students' overall well-being

According to the results of the gathered data, the subscale "Effect of poor sleep habits on students' overall well-being" has a weighted mean of 3.14 and a standard deviation of 0.14, which means that the respondents "Agreed," with the items listed on the said subscale. A mean of 3.26 and a standard deviation of 0.92 (strongly agreed) that they have missed assignments or exams due to insufficient sleep. While a mean of 3.00 and a standard deviation of 0.92 (agreed) to have trouble in understanding the lessons due to poor sleep. Table 2 also reveals a mean of 3.32 and a standard deviation of 0.71 (strongly agreed) that the lack of sleep affects the respondent's ability to concentrate on their studies. Moreover, A mean of 3.08 and a standard deviation of 0.86 (agreed) that sleep habits have a significant impact on their academic performance. Hershner and Chervin (2014) imply that there is an association between students' performance in school and their sleep quality. Academic performance has been linked to sleep deprivation; when a person fails to get enough sleep night after night, their ability to learn—including their memory, attentiveness, and problem-solving abilities—is significantly impacted. Students who deal with all the problems are likely to have lower grade point averages. (Chiang et al. 2014). Moreover, A mean of 3.30 and a standard deviation of 0.65 (strongly agreed) In the question "Does sleep habits affect your physical health like your energy levels and immune system ". Table 2 also obtains a mean of 2.92 and a standard deviation of 0.89 (agreed) that sleep issues contribute to feelings of anxiety or depression. Lastly, a mean of 3.14 and a standard deviation of 0.82 (agreed) that poor sleep habits negatively impact the respondent's mental health and overall well-being.

Students coping mechanism.

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation on the coping mechanism of the students. The corresponding subscale has a weighted mean of 2.79 and a standard deviation of 0.17, indicating that most respondents "Agreed" on the matter. In a study conducted by Baqutayan (2015), they have concluded that coping mechanisms affect people by changing how they view and respond to stressful situations, in addition to influencing the quality of their sleep. A mean of 2.77 and a standard deviation of 0.72 (agreed) that they participate in physical activities like exercise to relieve the stress brought on by lack of sleep. While a mean of 2.70 and a standard deviation of 0.92 (agreed) that the respondents engage in relaxation activities, such as yoga or meditation, to manage stress from poor sleep. In the question, "Do you spend time with your friends or family members to alleviate stress caused by poor sleep habits?" a mean of 2.94 and a standard deviation of 0.72 (agreed) has been obtained. On the other hand, there is a mean of 2.49 and standard deviation of 0.88 (Disagree), on the question if they use relaxation techniques like deep breathing, meditation to manage stress caused by poor sleep. This table also reveals that there is a mean of 2.98 and a standard deviation of 0.73 (agreed) on students consuming caffeinated beverages to counteract the effects of insufficient sleep. Lastly, 2.86 mean and 0.67 (Agreed) to practice self-care like focusing on health and nutrition to prevent the adverse effects of poor sleep.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of the Survey Questionnaires Results

Benchmark Statements for Poor Sleep Habits	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Demographic Profile's Influences on Students Stress Level			
1. Does the academic strand you are enrolled in affect your sleep patterns and overall stress?	3.08	0.77	Agree
2. Do you feel that your grade level has a significant impac on your sleep quality?	2.76	0.87	Agree
3. Does your stress level being influenced by the academic requirements associated with your current grade level ?	3.13	0.71	Agree
4. Does your gender play a role in how stressed you are as a student?	2.41	0.86	Disagree
Weighted Mean	2.84	0.28	Agree

Effect of poor sleep habits on students' overall well-being

1. Do you miss assignments or exams due to insufficient sleep?	3.26	0.92	Strongly Agree
2. Do you have trouble in understanding the lessons due to poor sleep ?	3.00	0.92	Agree

3. Does Lack of sleep affects your ability to concentrate on your studies ?	3.32	0.71	Strongly Agree
4. Do you think your sleep habits have a significant impact on your academic performance?	3.08	0.86	Agree
5. Does your sleep habits affect your physical health (e.g., energy levels, immune system).	3.30	0.65	Strongly Agree
6. Do Sleep issues contribute to feelings of anxiety or depression ?	2.92	0.89	Agree
7. Do you think poor sleep habits negatively impact your mental health and overall well-being?	3.14	0.82	Agree
Weighted Mean	3.14	0.14	Agree

Students Coping Mechanism

1. Do you participate in physical activities like exercise to relieve the stress brought on by lack of sleep.	2.77	0.72	Agree
2. Do you engage in relaxation activities, such as yoga or meditation, to manage stress from poor sleep.	2.70	0.92	Agree
3. Do you spend time with your friends or family members to alleviate stress caused by poor sleep habits?	2.94	0.72	Agree
4. Do you use relaxation techniques (e.g., deep breathing, meditation) to manage stress caused by poor sleep.	2.49	0.88	Disagree
5. Do you consume caffeinated beverages (e.g., coffee, energy drinks) to counteract the effects of insufficient sleep.	2.98	0.73	Agree
6. Do you practice self-care like focusing on health and nutrition to prevent the adverse effects of poor sleep?	2.86	0.67	Agree
Weighted Mean	2.79	0.16	Agree
Grand Weighted Mean	2.85	0.17	Agree

The sleep habits of the students

12 respondents had an 8 - 9 pm bedtime which is equivalent to 16 percent, while there are 23 respondents who answered 10-11 pm as their bedtime during weekdays that is equivalent to 30. 67 percent. Most of the respondents answered 12 - 1 am as their bedtime during weekends, specifically 40 respondents, which is equivalent to 50 .33 percent of respondents. On the other hand, 0 respondents answered 6 - 7 pm as their

bedtime during the weekdays. In the question about the respondents' bedtime during weekends, 11 students had a bedtime of 8 - 9 pm during the weekends, equivalent to 14.66 percent. While the number of respondents who have a bedtime of 10 - 11 pm and 12 - 1 am tied. 32 respondents answered 10 - 11 pm as their bedtime during the weekends, equivalent to 42.67. Similarly, 32 respondents answered 12 - 1 am as their bedtime during the weekends, equivalent to 42.67. On the other hand, no respondents answered 6 - 7 pm as their sleeping time during the weekends. In the hours of sleep of the respondents on Weekdays, an average of 2.67 percent have 10 - 11 sleeping hours, equivalent to 2 respondents. While 12 respondents, equivalent to 16 percent answered 8 - 9 sleeping hours on weekends. 30 respondents had 4 - 5 sleeping hours equivalent to 40 percent. Most of the respondents had sleeping hours of 6 - 7 on weekdays, equivalent to 41.33 percent. The 9 respondents, equivalent to 12 percent claimed that they have 10 - 11 hours of sleep during the weekdays. While an average of 21.33 percent, equivalent to 16 respondents have 4 - 5 sleeping hours. An average of 28 percent has 8-9 sleeping hours on weekends. Lastly, most of the respondents had 6 - 7 sleeping hours equivalent to 29 respondents during the weekends.

Table 3. Sleep Habits

Sleep Patterns	Frequency	%
Bed Time on weekdays		
6 - 7 pm	0	0
8 - 9 pm	12	16 %
10 - 11 pm	23	30.67%
12 - 1 am	40	50.33 %
Bed Time on weekends		
6 - 7 pm	0	0
8 - 9 pm	11	14.66 %
10 - 11 pm	32	42.67 %
12 - 1 am	32	42.67 %
Hours of sleep on weekdays		
4 - 5 Hours	30	40 %
6 - 7 Hours	31	41.33 %
8- 9 Hours	12	16 %
Hours of sleep on weekends		
10 - 11 Hours	2	2.67 %
4 - 5 Hours	16	21.33 %
6 - 7 Hours	29	38.67 %
8 - 9 Hours	21	28 %

Conclusions

The following are the conclusions in accordance with the summary of the results.

1. The respondents of this study are the Humanities and Social Sciences students, mostly female students. In terms of age, the respondents range from ages 16–19-year-old. Most of the respondents are Grade 12.
2. The researchers have drawn from the study that academic strands, grade levels, and academic requirements significantly influence the sleep patterns, stress levels, and ultimately, the overall well-being of the respondents. Additionally, while there is a disagreement on gender's impact on students' stress levels, the weighted mean indicates that demographic profiles do have an impact on stress levels among students.
3. The study's analysis of respondents' bedtime routines on weekdays and weekends, along with the number of hours of sleep they received, indicates that a significant number of respondents had inconsistent sleep schedules and insufficient sleep, especially on weekdays. This aligns with the reported impacts on academic performance, concentration, and mental health issues.
4. The researchers have drawn from the study that students often take part in a variety of activities to combat the stress-causing effects of sleep deprivation. Students use a variety of ways to reduce stress caused by sleep deprivation, including self-care, relaxation techniques, physical activity, and social interaction with family and friends, and consumption of caffeinated beverages.
5. The humanities and social sciences strand students at a higher educational institution situated in Pampanga often face challenges in maintaining proper sleep habits, and this has led to the continuous stress issues of students. The impact of stress on students does not only affect their physical health; rather, it creates a detrimental effect on their overall quality of life. There are also coping techniques that students employ that are not very appropriate, like the consumption of caffeinated beverages.

Recommendations

In line with the findings and conclusion of the study, the researchers arrived at the proceeding recommendations:

1. Facilitate and promote healthy coping strategies in the educational setting, such as exercising, practicing mindfulness, and taking care of oneself. Encourage

students to include these activities in their regular routine and inform them of the risks associated with using caffeinated beverages as a remedy for insufficient sleep.

2. Educators should conscientiously evaluate academic requirements, ensuring a balanced workload that does not overwhelm students with excessive assignments or tasks. This will make it possible to strike a healthier balance between students' wellbeing and their academic responsibilities.
3. Incorporating sleep education into the curriculum to help the students be enlightened on how important proper sleep hygiene is to their general health and academic success. By implementing this, students will get the knowledge and skills necessary to prioritize and control their sleep schedules to improve their overall state of well-being. By doing this, parents will also be enlightened about their children's sleep habits.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research strictly adheres to the ethical standards set by the institution and the body of knowledge. All information and data coming from the respondents are solely for academic purposes only. In line also with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researchers strictly preserved the anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents.

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